

MAGIC

Marginal lands for Growing Industrial Crops

D1.9. – Final version of MAGIC-CROPS and uploading in the project website

Due date of deliverable: M48 (30.06.2021)
Actual submission date: M49 (01.08.2021)

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Type

R Document, report

DEM Demonstrator, pilot, prototype

DEC Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.

OTHER

Dissemination Level

PU Public

CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 727698.

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1 Executive summary

The MAGIC-CROPS database is an easy-to-use tool including 37 promising non-food species suited to marginal land as defined in the JRC's report (EUR 23412 EN - 2008 and later modifications). Additionally, to biophysical constraints referred in the above-mentioned report, the MAGIC-CROPS database includes also information about the suitability of some species to soil contaminated by heavy metals. The present deliverable is the final version of the MAGIC-CROPS database and all the 37 crops are included. Twenty out of the 37 species included in the database are under-study in WP4 of the MAGIC project, so in the event that important new insights will come out after the publication of the present deliverable, the MAGIC-CROPS database will be updated accordingly by the end of the project (31.12.2021).

2 Introduction

This final version of the MAGIC-CROPS database includes all the 37 crops identified by the MAGIC consortium as the most suitable to be grown in marginal soils. For all the crops, a general description, and specific scores to rank them across their tolerance to biophysical constraints are provided. The information has been taken from literature and own knowledge of the partners, as well as from MAGIC trials. Noteworthy, contaminated land was not included in the JRC's report on marginality factors (EUR 23412 EN - 2008 and later modifications), but it is included in the MAGIC database.

3 User-guide for the MAGIC-CROPS Database

Light-yellow section (see below): general description of each crop including the common names. The lead partner of the crop is indicated in the first column.

Light-green section: scores indicating the crop suitability to biophysical constraints. In particular from 1 to 3 indicate respectively a yield reduction of >50%, between 25% and 50%, and <25%. Zero indicates a crop that is not affected by the specific constrain; NA means that information is not available. The scores in response to heavy metal contamination reported in the last four columns are derived from Task 4.3.2 of MAGIC project at double EU limits of contamination for the considered heavy metal.

Light blue section: key management agricultural practices under marginal land (e.g., propagation material, its availability, the maximum and minimum temperatures for growing, etc.

Light grey section: main qualitative traits of feedstocks, current uses and possible new applications/market.

4 Updated version of MAGIC-CROPS Database

The [MAGIC-CROPS database](#) is an excel file which acts as data source for the MAGIC decision support system and GIS maps. Being the participant portal only supporting pdf files, we show later on some snapshots of the database.

Lead partner	Latin name	Common name	Other names	General description	
					Short description
UNIBO	<i>Panicum virgatum</i> L.	Switchgrass			Perennial herbaceous warm-season grass (C4) native to Northern America. Erect and caespitose plant, 1-3 m tall. Associated to their latitudinal origin, cultivars of switchgrass can be placed into two distinct ecotypes: upland and lowland. Upland ecotypes are better adapted to the drier and colder habitats, while lowlands tends to thrive in warmer, wetter habitats.
UNIBO	<i>Camelina sativa</i> (L.) Crantz	Camelina	False flax, Gold of pleasure		Annual oilseed crop native (C3) to Eurasia. Plants are erect (0.8-1.2 m tall). Each branch terminate in a raceme with yellow flowers typical of Brassicaceae family. Up to 10-12 seeds are enclosed in a "pear-shape" silique. Individual seed weight is below 1.5 mg. Both spring and winter biotypes are available in the market.
CRES	<i>Sorghum bicolor</i> (L.) Moench	Sorghum			It's a C4 grass species largely grown in warm climate worldwide. Different types exist with different end-uses covering: food and non-food application. Plant morphology is depending to the end-uses, sugar and biomass types can be as tall as 4 m. Sorghum is characterized by high water use efficiency compared to corn
WUR	<i>Crambe abyssinica</i> Hochst x R.E. Fries	Crambe	Abyssinian crambe, Abyssinian kale; bolletjeskool (NL)		annual industrial oilcrop, origin in the Mediterranean and in highlands of east Africa, well adapted to the cool and wet climate conditions of large parts of Europe. Belongs to the <i>Brassicaceae</i> . Plant height ~116-183 cm (average 120); root depth ~15cm; total above round biomass 400 - 600 g m ⁻² ; need spring rainfall, WUE ~63 kg ha ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
CRES	<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	Castorbean	Palm of Christ		Oilseed species belonging to the Euphorbiaceae family. It's a summer annual species which can grow also a perennial in tropical climate. Plants can grow up to 3 m tall, but dwarf hybrids are now available on the market to allow mechanical harvest. Seeds are characterized by oil content >50%, but the toxic compound ricin is also present.
UHOH	<i>Miscanthus x giganteus</i>	Miscanthus			Perennial rhizomatous grass native to East Asia. High biomass yield potential due to C4 photosynthetic mechanism. <i>Miscanthus x giganteus</i> is presently the only commercially grown miscanthus genotype. It is a triploid, sterile hybrid between <i>Miscanthus sinensis</i> and <i>Miscanthus sacchariflorus</i> .
UNICT	<i>Arundo donax</i> L.	Giant reed	Common reed, Giant cane		Perennial herbaceous warm-season grass (C3) native to Asia, endemic in Mediterranean areas. Erect and caespitose plant, 2-5 m tall. Sterile plant, propagate exclusively by vegetative propagules (rhizomes, stem cuttings, node cuttings). Small degree of genetic variation due to clonal reproduction, but phenotypic variation has observed between the <i>A. donax</i> ecotypes according to their colonization sites. It is able to thrive in hot, drought prone environments, as well as wetter habitats, under salinity, steep slopes, poor soil texture and contaminated soil.
CIEMAT	<i>Agropyron elongatum</i> (Host.) Beauv.	Tall wheatgrass			The plants commonly known as "agropiros" belong to several genera: <i>Agropyron</i> , <i>Pascopyrum</i> , <i>Thinopyrum</i> , <i>Elymus</i> , <i>Elytrigia</i> . Perennial herbaceous plants of gramineas family, adapted to a wide variety of soils and arid regions of cold climate. They have great resistance to dry climates and extreme temperatures. In Spain its use as an energy crop is in experimental plots.
UHOH	<i>Amaranthus spp.</i>	Amaranth			Amaranth is an annual dicotyledonous monoecious (self-pollinating) warm-season plant (>3 m tall) native to Southern America. Amaranth was used as a grain crop since millennia due to its high nutritional value. The use of amaranth for biogas production is under investigation and promising due to both its C4 photosynthetic pathway and its high water use efficiency. Additionally, a high heavy metal uptake efficiency could render amaranth suitable for phytomining or phytoremediation purposes on contaminated marginal land.
UNICT	<i>Helianthus annus</i> L.	Sunflower	Common sunflower		Sunflower is a large annual, warm-season forb belonging to the Asteraceae family. It is adapted to a wide range of environments, from tropical to continental. Very tolerant to drought. Sunflower is mainly used as a source of edible seed oil, for seed direct consumption or as ornamental and industrial purposes. High oleic hybrids commonly grown are well suited to oleochemical applications
UNIBO	<i>Brassica carinata</i> A. Braun.	Ethiopian mustard	carinata		Belonging to the Brassicaceae family, <i>carinata</i> is a low input crop, very tolerant to different biotic and abiotic stresses, and also to seed shattering. Plants are highly vigorous and they can present both white and yellow flowers. Despite being a spring crop in mild environments it could be grown also as a winter crop.
UNICT	<i>Cannabis sativa</i> L.	Hemp	Industrial hemp, fiber hemp, seed hemp		Hemp is an annual, dicotyledonous, warm-season (C3) plant belonging to the Cannabaceae family, adapted to a wide range of environments. Naturally it is dioecious, with the male plants that are taller and that come to flower earlier that the female ones. It is wind pollinated and the male plants die after producing millions of pollen grains. Monoecious varieties have been elected in modern times to reduce some agronomic problems such as an efficient mechanization for harvesting the seeds, and the lower fibre quality and yield losses encountered when harvesting dioecious varieties at seed maturity

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IWNIRZ	<i>Linum usitatissimum L.</i>	Flax	Linseed (oil flax), fiber flax	Annual oilseed and fiber crop native to Mediterranean basin and middle east. Panicle with numerous branches terminated with mostly blue and white flowers. Fruit - capsules with up to 10 seeds. Average 1000-seed weight 6-8 g. Mostly spring crop available in market.
LSFRI SILAVA	<i>Phalaris arundinaceae L.</i>	Reed canary grass		Widely spread as native species growing in Europa as well in North America and Asia. Grass is a sod- forming, productive, vigorous, perennial (up to 7 years rotation). Plant has dominantly basal broad and moderately harsh, erect leaves on coarse, erect stems. Height of 1.5 to 2 m. The storage life of seeds is short, just 5 years. Seed quality should be checked for germination within 6 months of its use. Starts in early spring and continues through the growing season. Reed canary grass RCG is well suited to wet soils that are poorly drained or subject to flooding (1-3 weeks below oxygen rich water) and survives well in drought, it also has excellent frost tolerance. Forage quality is good prior to heading but then declines rapidly, overgrown stems could be used as solid biofuels fresh biomass for biogas production. Regrowth after grazing and/ or mowing is very rapid on fertile sites and good on poor sites.
UNIBO	<i>Phragmites australis (Cav.) Trin. ex Steud.</i>	Common reed		Cosmopolitan perennial wetland grass, absent only above and below the latitude of 70° N and S. Phylogeographic diversity and high phenotypic plasticity. Up to 6 m tall depending on genetics, ploidy and habitat. High ecological tolerance, including draught, salt and disturbance. Not domesticated, mostly harvested from nature. Very few cultivation experiences (paludiculture).
CIEMAT	<i>Spartium junceum L.</i>	Spanish broom	Retama	Species is native to the Mediterranean in southern Europe, southwest Asia and northwest Africa, where it is found in sunny sites, usually on dry, sandy soils. Spartium is a species of flowering plant in the family Fabaceae. Spartium could be used to produced biomass in short rotation, biomass yields are about 6 -10 tdm/ha year), because Spartium has high regrowth capacity and is a good N fixer in the soil.
CRES	<i>Carthamus dictorius L.</i>	Safflower		Highly branched, herbaceous, thistle-like annual plant. Plants can be up to 2 m tall. Differently from sunflower, safflower is able to withstand low temperature, and winter types are available. It is commercially cultivated for vegetable oil extracted from the seeds but also as a source of orange-yellow pigments. High oleic hybrids are also available in the market as for sunflower
IWNIRZ	<i>Urtica dioica L.</i>	Nettle	Stinging nettle	Perennial fiber and medicinal plant crop. Native to Europe and Asia. Dioecious or monoecious plant, stems are single or sparsely and lightly branched, usually with a height of 0.4 m to 1 m, although sometimes reaching up to 3 m high.
UNICT	<i>Cynara cardunculus L.</i>	Cardoon	Cardoon, Cynara, Castile thistle	Cardoon is a perennial, dicot, herbaceous, lignocellulosic (C3) plant belonging to the Compositae (Asteraceae) family, closely related to globe artichoke (<i>C. cardunculus</i> var. <i>scolymus</i> (L.)), native to Mediterranean environments. It has been traditionally cultivated as vegetable in Mediterranean regions for century to produce edible stalks. For bioenergy purpose, it is a good candidate to be grown in the dry lands of the Mediterranean region as lignocellulosic and oilseed crop. The seeds are rich in oil and could be mechanically harvested separately from the rest of the biomass.
WUR	<i>Parthenium argentatum A.Gray</i>	Guayule		Guayule is a shrub, belonging to the Asteraceae family, originally growing in semi-arid regions in Mexico and the Southern USA; well suited to the semi-arid areas of Southern Europe; It is introduced as a biennial or multiannual crop for the production of rubber; irrigation needed 500-1300mm.
UNIBO	<i>Thlaspi arvense L.</i>	Pennycress	Stinkweed, field pennycress, fanweed, frenchweed, bastard cress, wild garlic	Pennycress is a common winter annual weed species, native of Eurasia, it is a C3 species. Although largely considered an agricultural weed, pennycress is an attractive biofuel feedstock as it can grow in a wide range of habitats and seeds are rich in oil.
IBC	<i>Salix spp.</i>	Willow	Sallow, Osier	The genus of deciduous woody plants includes 350-370 species. Most willow species can be easily reproduced with winter cuttings. For energy feedstock, fast-growing cultivars of <i>Salix viminalis</i> L. and closely related species are grown. Willow does not require rich soil; it can grow in low-fertile and acidic soil, but requires a lot of moisture. Therefore, plantations of energy willow should be established in the areas of adequate moisture, floodplains, and other places with high levels of groundwater.
LSFRI SILAVA	<i>Populus spp.</i>	Poplar	White poplar, Balsam poplar, Lombardy poplar, Cottonwood, Aspen poplar and others Poplar is name of genus containing several species.	(Plants) any tree of the salicaceous genus <i>Populus</i> , of N temperate regions, having triangular leaves, flowers borne in catkins, and light soft wood. It's a fast-growing plant which adapt well to biofuel production as short rotation coppice. Poplar is very vigorous and it can grow up to 40-m tall in moisture rich soils.

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CRES	<i>Robinia pseudoacacia L.</i>	Black locust	False acacia	It is a medium-sized hardwood deciduous tree. It is a leguminous species able to fix atmospheric nitrogen. Being native of eastern USA black locust became an endemic invasive species also in Europe. Plants can grow up to 30 m tall. Robinia is a honey plant and its wood finds several applications as solid fuel.
FCT UNL	<i>Eucalyptus spp.</i>	Eucalyptus		Eucalyptus is a highly adaptive and fast-growing flowering trees species (C3) from the Myrtaceae family. With most than 700 subspecies, mainly native from Australia is very well implemented in Mediterranean Europe, mainly in the Iberic Peninsula. Adult plants attain a height of up to 90 m. Eucalyptus species can be grown successfully not only in the regions where they occur naturally, but in the most parts of the tropics, subtropics and warm temperate zones.
CIEMAT	<i>Ulmus pumila L.</i>	Siberian elm	Littleleaf elm	Siberian elm is native to Asia, widely distributed throughout China, Korea, Mongolia, East Russia and Central Asia. Siberian is resistance to Dutch elm disease and adaptation to all growing conditions, particularly its hardiness, drought tolerance and adaptation to different environments. In Spain it grows naturalized in ditches, slopes and marginal lands. Siberian elm is an extremely hardy tree, deciduous, rapidly-growing to 25 m tall . It could be used to produced biomass in short rotation coppice.
UNICT	<i>Saccharum spontaneum L. aegyptiacum</i>	Wild sugarcane	African fodder cane	Perennial herbaceous warm-season grass (C4) native to from Egypt, endemic in Sicily. Erect and caespitose plant, 1.5-4 m tall. Sterile plant, propagated exclusively by vegetative propagules (rhizomes). Small degree of genetic variation due to clonal reproduction, wide distribution on sites close coastal sea. It is able to thrive in hot, drought prone environments, as well as wetter habitats, steep slopes, sandy and poor soil textured.
WU	<i>Lupinus mutabilis Sweet</i>	Lupin	Tarwi, Chocho, tremoço	Lupinus mutabilis is an annual C3 crop of the Fabaceae family. It is mostly a self-pollinating species but depending on the genotype and climate it can experience up to 30% cross-pollination. It is one of the "new world" lupin species with a center of origin and diversity in the Andes. It is a robust crop tolerant to salt and low temperatures. Its initially application was as protein crop, but given the high yield of biomass produced, namely stems and leaves, it has become an interesting crop for biobased applications.
CRES	<i>Nicotiana glauca Graham</i>	Wild tobacco (tree)	Tree tobacco	Tree tobacco is native to South America but it is now widespread as an introduced species on other continents. It's an evergreen shrub growing up to 3 m by 3 m. It contains the toxic alkaloid anabasine and ingestion of the leaves can be fatal. It is being investigated for use as a biofuel.
CRES	<i>Atriplex spp.</i>	Saltbush	Orache, Orach	Belonging to the Chenopodiaceae family, it can be an annual or perennial shrub. It's able to grow under desert conditions, and shores under high salinity levels. Leaves are able to retain salts. It can be used for soil rehabilitation of mining sites.
UNIBO	<i>Helianthus tuberosus L.</i>	Jerusalem artichoke	topinambur, sunchoke, sunroot, earth apple	Perennial herbaceous tuberous species (C3) native to the southern states of North America, 1.5-2 m tall. Grown both for the tubers and for the stems, it adapts to a wide range of climatic conditions. Particularly relevant is the inulin content (especially in tubers), a fructose polymer with both medical and nutritional implications. Allogamous species, it reproduces mainly agamically and rapidly colonizes the areas in which it grows spontaneously.
CRES	<i>Hibiscus cannabunus L.</i>	Kenaf	Deccan hemp, Java jute	It's a native species of Asia which has been introduces worldwide. It is an annual or biennial herbaceous plant growing to 1.5-3.5 m tall. From the stem, 20-25% of bast fibers are obtained with outstanding insulation properties. From seeds an oil with food and non-food uses is obtained.
UNIBO	<i>Crotalaria juncea L.</i>	Sunn hemp	brown hemp, Indian hemp, Madras hemp	Annual summer legume (C3), native to India. It is a fast growing and high yielding lignocellulosic crop with a great potential as a feedstock for advanced biofuels. Even though its tropical origin, sunn hemp could be cultivated in temperate climates where it can reach 1.2 m height in 60 days. It can be integrated into traditional cropping system, increasing crop diversification, soil fertility (N fixed into the soil)
UNIBO	<i>Euphorbia lagascae Spreng.</i>	Caper spurge / euphorbia	wild spurge, vernin spurge, moleplant	It's an annual spurge native to south-eastern Spain and Italy (Sardinia). It produces a central primary shoot, which can reach 1m height, and the secondary shoots connect to the base of this. The generative organ is called cyathium (characteristic inflorescence of the spurges). It consists of a cup-shaped involucre of fused bracts enclosing several greatly reduced male flowers and a single female flower. Uneven maturation creates problems at harvest.
IBC	<i>Beta vulgaris L.</i>	Sugar beets		Due to a high concentration of sucrose in roots, sugar beet is grown as a feedstock for sugar and ethanol production. Sugar beet can be grown worldwide in regions without severe frosts. It prefers relatively cool temperature between 15 and 19 °C. The ancestors being coastal plants, sugar beet tolerate saline soil and drought. The crop grows best in rich soils with additional introduction of Sodium and Boron.
WUR	<i>Calendula officinalis L.</i>	Calendula	Common marigold, pot marigold	A aromatic, herbaceous perennial, belongs to the Asteraceae family, origin in the Mediterranean but worldwide adapted to warm temperate regions. The plant can grow to 80 cm tall, and is sparsely branched. The flowerhead gas a single or double row of florets, surrounding the central disk flowers. It can grow on a wide range of soil types. It does not need much water or fertilization. Although grown as an annual crop,

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				calendula is actually a short-lived perennial. Seed germinated between 2 and 32°C with the optimum germination temperature at 16–17 °C. Heat shock temperatures (35-40°C) <50 h duration, will reduce the germination below 50%. Soil pH for optimal growth pH=5.5-7; seeds harvested 115 to 120 d after seeding.
INRA	<i>Lavandula angustifolia</i> Miller, <i>Lavandula angustifolia</i> L., <i>L. intermedia</i> Emeric	True lavender English lavender Lavandin	Spike lavender	Small, non-hardy perennial evergreen shrub native to the Mediterranean, with a typical productive life of about 10 years. It can grow on coarse, rocky soils, and coastal climates.

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CROPS	Crop performance in land with specific biophysical constraints																		
	Low Temp.		Dryness	Soil moisture	Soil drainage	Soil texture				Shallow rooting depth	Salinity	Sodicity	Acidity	Steep Slope	Contaminated soil (general info)	Ni contaminated soil	Cd contaminated soil	Pb contaminated soil	Zn contaminated soil
	GSL <195d	GDD <1575 T base 5°C	P/PET <0.6	FC >210d	Poorly or very poorly drained	Coarse material >10%	Sand; loamy sand >40%	Clay>50%	OM>30% (30/100 cm)	<35cm	>3.2 dS/m	>4.8 ESP	pH<5.5	>12%	Soils contaminated with metals and post-mortem landfills				
	Score: 1 to 3 [YR=yield (actual) reduction]: 1= YR>50%; 2= 25%< YR <50%; 3= YR < 25%; 0= Unfeasible																		
Switchgrass	2	2	2	3	2	2	3	3	NA	2	3	3	3	2	2	3	3	3	0
Camelina	3	3	3	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	NA	NA	1	2	3	1	3	3
Sorghum	3	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	NA	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	3	2	0
Crambe	3	3	2	2	1	1	3	3	3	2	2	NA	3	NA	2	3	2	3	3
Castorbean	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	NA	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	3	0
Miscanthus	3	1	2	2	2	3	3	1	3	2	2	NA	3	3	1	3	2	3	3
Giant reed	1	1	2	3	3	2	3	3	NA	1	3	NA	NA	2	2	2	2	2	2
Tall wheatgrass	3	2	3	2	1	3	3	1	NA	2	3	NA	3	2	NA	*	*	*	*
Amaranth	2	1	2	1	1	2	3	1	1	3	3	NA	3	1	2				
Sunflower	3	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	NA	1	2	NA	0	NA	1				
Ethiopian mustard			2	2	1	1	3	3	3	2	2	NA	NA	2	2	2	3	3	3
Hemp	2	2	2	1	1	1	3	0	NA	0	1	NA	0	NA	2	*	*	*	*
Flax	3	3	2	1	1	3	2	1	2	3	1	1	3	3	3				
Reed canary grass	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	2				
Common reed	3	3	0	3	3	3	3	3	NA	0	1	NA	NA	2	3				
Spanish broom	NA	NA	3	2	1	3	3	1	NA	1	3	NA	2	2	NA				
Safflower	2	2	2	0-1	1	2	2	1	NA	1	2	NA	1	2	2	*	*	*	*
Nettle	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	NA	2	NA	NA	3	3	3				
Cardoon	0	0	3	1	1	2	2	2	NA	2	3	3	3	2	2	*	*	*	*
Guayule	0	0	NA	NA	NA	3	3	NA	NA	0	2	NA	NA	3	..				
Pennycress	3	3	0	2	2	1	NA	NA	NA	3	2	NA	NA	1	3	*	*	*	*
Willow	3	3	1	3	2	3	3	2	2	2	1	3	3	2	3				
Poplar	2	2	2	3	1	3	3	3	3	1	2	3	1	NA	1				
Black locust	1	2	2	1	1	2	2		NA	1				3	2				
Eucalyptus	1 to 0	1 to 0	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	3	3	3				
Siberian elm	3	3	3	2	1	3	3	1	NA	0	0	NA	2	2	NA				
Wild sugarcane	0	0	3	3	3	2	3	2	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	3	1	2	1
Lupin	NA	3	2	2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	*	*	*	*
Wild tobacco	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	NA	1	2	2	2	2	NA				
Saltbush	1 to 2	2	2	1	1	2	1 to 2	1	NA	2	2	NA	1	3	NA				
Jerusalem artichoke	1	1	2	1	2	NA	3	1	NA	NA	2	2	2	3	3				
Kenaf	0	1	1	1	0-1	1	2	2	NA	2	2	1	1	1	2				

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Sunn hemp	1	1	2	3	1	3	3	2	2	3	1	NA	3	3	NA				
Caper spurge	0	0	3	0	0	NA	2	3	NA	NA	2	NA	1	NA	NA				
Sugar beets	3	3	1	2	1	2	3	1	3	1	3	3	1	2	2				
Calendula	3	3	2	NA	2	3	3	3	NA	NA	2		NA	NA	3				
True lavender	0	0	3	3	0	3	3	0	NA	3	2	NA	2	3	NA				

* trials on Task 4.3.2 are ongoing and data are not available yet.

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CROPS	Cultivation under marginal land									
	Propagation	Availability of genetic material	Temp Min/Max	Cycle	Plant density	Fertilization (NPK)	Harvesting period	Harvesting method	Potential production	Main product
Switchgrass	Seed	High	10-35	Perennial	50-150	50-100 Kg N/y 80-100 kg P (only at establishment) 80-100 kg K (only at establishment)	Summer to spring	Baled straw	15 Mg/ha/y (DM)	Lignocellulose
Camelina	Seed	High	0-30	Annual	200-300	50-70 Kg N/ha 50-60 kg P/y 30-50 kg K/y	Spring to summer	Combine threshing	2.5 Mg/ha (seeds)	Oil
Sorghum	Seed	High	12-35	Annual (spring)	11-44	100-150 kg N, 60-100 kg P2O5 and 60-100 kg K2O per hectare	Summer to early fall	Chopped	20-35 Mg/ha (DM)	Lignocellulose
Crambe	Seed	High	6.8 - 30	Annual	100-200	30-75Kg N/ha (or adapted to soil reserves); 40-80kg P/ha; 60-90kg K/ha	spring to summer	Combine threshing	1.3-3 Mg/ha (seeds), ~800kg/ha (oil)	Oil
Castorbean	Seed	Medium	12-35	Annual/perennial	6-10		Summer to early fall	Combined threshing	3-5 Mg/ha/y (seeds), 6-10 Mg/ha/y (straw)	Oil
Miscanthus	Rhizome, micropropagation; seeded hybrids are under development	High	8 - 45	Perennial	1 - 2	0 - 50 kg N/y; 40 kg P/y; 80 kg K/y	Solid fuel and building material: February to March; Biogas: October	Baled straw or Chips	40 Mg DM/ha/y	Lignocellulose
Giant reed	Rhizome, cuttings	Low	10-45	Perennial	1-2.5	50-100 Kg N/y	Fall to winter	Chopped	30 Mg/ha/y (DM)	Lignocellulose
Tall wheatgrass	Seed	Medium	15-25	Perennial	400-500	55 kg N/ha	Summer	Baled straw	5-7 Mg/ha/y (DM)	Lignocellulose
Amaranth	Seed	Low	12-35	Annual	30	150 kg N; 50 kg P; 100 kg K	Late summer / early fall	Chopped	8-15 Mg DM/ha	Lignocellulose
Sunflower	Seed	High	8-34	Annual	2-3	130-90-350 (NPK)	Summer to early fall	Combine harvester	2.5 Mg DM/ha seeds	Oil
Ethiopian mustard	Seed	Medium	4-30	Annual	50-120	0-70 Kg N/ha 50-60 kg P/ha 30-50 kg K/ha	Summer	Combine threshing	1-3 Mg/ha DM	Oil
Hemp	Seed	High	10-30	Annual	30-75 (seed); 150-250 (fiber)	60-120 Kg N/ha	Summer to Fall	Double-cut combine	1.0-1.5 Mg/ha (seeds), 8-15 Mg/ha (dry stems)	Oil, fiber
Flax	Seed	High	4-30	Annual	400 (seed); 1200 (fiber)	30-40 P, 120-140 K, 30-40 N (fiber flax), 70-90 N (linseed)	Summer	Combine/specialised machines	Seeds: up to 3 Mgt/ha Straw: up to 6 Mg/ha	Oil, Fibre
Reed canary grass	Seeds, Rhizomes	High	5-30	Perennial	200-300	60 Kg N/ha	Summer to Spring	Baled straw or Combine threshing	Biomass - non-fertilized 3.67 t /ha to 5.73 Mg/ha, fertilized increase by 1.93 Mg/ha (+37%); Could be increased by two cuts – annual dry matter yields ranged from: 3.93–11.44 Mg/ha in two-cut and 5.89–13.94 Mg/ha In single-cut regime; seeds 129-373 kg/ha depending of N availability	Lignocellulose

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Common reed	rhizome, cutting	Low	NA	perennial	5-8	100-150 kg/ha/y of N 100-120 kg/ha of P (establishment) 90-100 kg/ha of K (establishment)	Summer to winter	Baled straw	5-20 Mg/ha/y (DM)	Lignocellulose
Spanish broom	Seed, plantlets	NA	15-22	Perennial	1	no need N	Winter	Baled	6-10 Mg/ha/y (DM)	Lignocellulose
Safflower	Seed	Low to medium	5-35	Annual	30-70		Summer to Spring	Combine harvester	1.5 to 3 Mg/ha/y (seeds)	oil
Nettle	Seed, mostly rhizomes	Low	8-30	Perennial	4	160-240 N kg/ha	Spring to fall depending on final use	Manual or mechanical	ephemeric fiber production, leaves widely used as medicinal industry	Biologically active substances, fiber
Cardoon	Seed or suckers	Medium	20-45	Perennial	3-15	50-50-100	Summer	Baled straw (forage harvester mounted with a robust header or a biomass harvester-baler)	3.7-13.8 Mg DM/ha/y (lignocellulose biomass), 0.5-1.5 Mg DM/ha/y (seeds)	Lignocellulose, Oil
Guayule	Seed, plantlets	High	10-49.5	Perennial	<10	0-210 N kg/ha; standard 40 N kg/ha	every 2 to 3 years, all seasons	mechanical	5.5 -15 Mg/ha/y (biomass); 0.32 - 1.9Mg/ha/y (rubber)	rubber, latex
Pennycress	Seed	Medium	0-30	Annual	80-150	50-50-50 kg/ha NPK	late spring	Combine threshing	1-1.5 Mg/ha (DM)	Oil
Willow	Cuttings	High	5-35	Perennial	1.2-1.5	20-30 Kg N/ha; 3 kg P/ha; 13 kg K/ha	Winter	Cut-and-chip harvesting	20 Mg/ha/y (DM)	Lignocellulose
Poplar	Stem cuttings of different size, seedlings from seeds or tissue cultures, root cuttings.	High	1-40	Perennial	Plants per ha :800-2000 rotation up to 5 years,) more plants rotation less than 5 years.	50-100 Kg N /ha y	All season usually leaveless – winter-spring-autumn	harvester, motor-manual, special self moving chippers	4-10 Mg DM/y, 250-450 m ³ /ha for 15-20 years, key factors are length of vegetation season and availability of nutrients.	energy wood, chips pellets, boards and furniture for sauna
Black locust	Invasive, seeds	Medium to high	5-40	Perennial			Winter every 3 to 5 years	Chopped and chipped		Lignocellulosic
Eucalyptus	Seeds, cuttings	High	5 - 30	Perennial	0.5-2	None to the limit of 40 kg (N)/ha; 18.8 kg (P2O5)/ha; 50 kg (K2O)/ha)	3-20 years	Mechanical harvesting: Cut-to-length	32	Lignocellulose
Siberian elm	Seed, plantlets	Medium/Low	15-25	Perennial	0.3-0,6	60 kg N/ha	Winter	Baled, chips	3-12 Mg/ha/y (DM)	Lignocellulose
Wild sugarcane	Rhizome, cuttings	Low	10-45	Perennial	1-2	50-100 Kg N/y	Fall to winter	Chopped	20 Mg/ha/y (DM)	Lignocellulose
Lupin										
Wild tobacco)	Invasive, seeds	Low		Perennial			Fall to winter			
Saltbush	Seeds	Low	0-35	Annual/perennial	0.1-0.3	112 Kg P/ha	Fall	Chopped	2-5 Mg/ha/y (straw)	Lignocellulose

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Jerusalem artichoke	Tuber	Medium	10-25	perennial crop, grown as an annual	5-8	130-150 Kg N/ha; 70-80 Kg P2O5/ha; 200-250 Kg K2O/ha	fall/winter	Machine harvest: tubers with potato picker and stems with mower.	90 Mg/ha/y of tubers (= 4-5 Mg/ha/y of carbohydrate)	Fresh tubers, carbohydrates
Kenaf	Seed	Medium	12-35	Annual (spring)	15-35		fall	Cut-and-chip harvesting or the machinery used for industrial hemp (depending on the end-use)	15-25 Mg/ha/y (DM)	Lignocellulose
Sunn hemp	Seed	Medium	10 - 30	Annual	30-50	100 kg P2O5 ha-1	Late summer, fall	Shredder + baler	10 - 15 Mg DM/ha/y	fiber, lignocellulose
Caper spurge	Seed	Medium	18-22	Annual	3.6-14.3	NA	Fall to spring	Machine harvest	0.4 to 1.6 Mg/ha	Oil, plant extracts
Sugar beets	Seed	High	2-40	Annual	8-10	90-150 kgN/ha, 60-90 kgP/ha, 90-180 kgK/ha	Autumn	Combine harvesting	Root yield 90-120 Mg/ha, sugar yield 14.4-19.2 Mg/ha	Sugar
Calendula	Seed	High	feb-32	Annual	30-60	0-100 kgN/ha; 0-150kgP/ha	spring	Combine harvesting	0.7-2.8 Mg/ha (seed)	specialty Oil
True lavender	Cuttings, seeds	medium	10-30	Perennial	2	80 kg N/ha	Summer	May be mechanized	50-100 kg oil/ha	Oil

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CROPS	Qualitative characteristics	Current uses	Innovative applications
Switchgrass	NDF= 75-80% ADF= 45-50% Lignin= 20-25% Ash= 2-3% Whole plant Higher Heating Value (HHV)= 18.8 MJ kg ⁻¹	Forage, CHP, erosion mitigation, wildlife habitat	Advanced biofuels, bioplastics, phytoremediation
Camelina	Seed: oil 35-42%, protein 25-30%. Main FAs: C18:1= 14-19%; C18:2=14-21%; C18:3=27-42%; C20:1=14-18%	Aquaculture, cosmetics, food and feed uses, aviation fuel, winter cover crop	Hydraulic fluids, biopolymers
Sorghum	Ash= 4-6%, Gross calorific value: 4400 kcal/kg	The seeds are used for feed and food application, the entire biomass or the residual biomass could be used for biogas production. Biomass sorghum and sweet sorghum are dedicated to non-food applications	As lignocellulosic feedstock for advanced biofuels, phytoremediation
Crambe	Seed oil 36-38%, seed protein 25-35%; Main FAs: C18:1= 17.2%; C18:2=8.7%; C18:3=5.2%; C22:1=56-60%;	erucamide (slip agent in plastics); high temperature resistant industrial lubricant; chemicals (erucyl alcohol, behenic acid, behenic alcohol); seed-meal, ad mixture up to 5% in cattle feed	Plant oil for oleo chemistry (metathesis) for novel products e.g. polymers; biodiesel
Castorbean	Oil content ~ 50%, 85% of the oil corresponding to ricin oleic acid, the ash content of the straw 6-8%, Gross calorific value: 4200 kcal/kg	Oil has different applications in the oleochemistry, in particular polymer production for textile and plastic materials	Oil can be converted into biofuels, It can be grown for phytoremediation
Miscanthus	Hemicellulose= 24 - 32% Cellulose= 28 - 49% Lignin= 15 - 28% Ash= 1.5 - 4% Whole plant Higher Heating Value (HHV)= 17.5 MJ kg ⁻¹	Solid fuel; Building material (Isolation, thatching, panels), animal bedding, biocomposites	Biogas, isobutanol (under investigation), erosion mitigation, other ecosystem services
Giant reed	Hemicellulose= 23-24% Cellulose= 35-38% Lignin= 20-22% Ash= 4-7% Whole plant Higher Heating Value (HHV)= 16-18 MJ kg ⁻¹	Fences, roofs, music instruments, paper	Advanced biofuels, bioplastics, non-wood materials, phytoremediation, erosion mitigation, other ecosystem services
Tall wheatgrass		Forage, erosion mitigation	Advanced biofuels
Amaranth	Dry matter content= 26% Hemicellulose= 11% Cellulose= 34% Lignin= 6.5% Ash= 13% Specific methane yield= 266 IN CH ₄ / kg VS	Grain, forage	Biogas, phytoremediation, phytomining, other ecosystem services (landscape heterogeneity, feed source for pollinators)
Sunflower	Seed: oil 30-45%, protein 20-22%, fiber 15%. 20-83% MUFAs and 4-65% PUFAs, 9-10% saturated FA	Food, feed, fuel	FAME biofuels, biogas, oil-platform products and lignocellulosic residue valorization
Ethiopian mustard	Seed: oil 30-38%, protein 28-33%. Main FAs: C18:1=8-13%, C18:2=12-15%, C18:3 =8-15%, C22:1=35-48%	Food, biofuel	Aviation fuel
Hemp	Seed: oil 30-35%, protein 20-25%. 13-19% MUFAs and 76-81% PUFAs	Food, textiles, ropes, composites materials, insulation mats, car interior panels, reinforce	Advanced biofuels, biogas, secondary metabolites (cannabinoids, terpenoids and flavonoids for pharmaceutical applications), bio-

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		expanded starch foams in the food packaging sector, hemp concrete	pesticides against nematodes, mesophilic fungi, insects and potentially weeds
Flax	Oil content ca 40%, total fiber content ca 30%, long fiber content ca 25%	Oil - food, pharmacy, cosmetics, chemicals, fiber - textiles, technical textiles	Composites, biologically active substances in medicine
Reed canary grass	Ash=6-8%, Carbon = 42-47%, H hydrogen = 5.4-5.9%, C/H = 1.51-1.52, N = 1,13%, Cl = 0.5-0.8%, P = 28%, K= 1.4-3.9%, S = 0.013%; energy production = 67.2 GJ/ha; Ash melting temperature -1240 °C	Solid biomass for pellets, Fodder, Fresh biomass for biogas, seed production	Drugs, granulated litter for small pets, biorefinery products, phytoremediation
Common reed	NA	Water treatment, roof thatching, paper and pulp, energy (combustion and biogas), fodder and litter	Bioconstruction material, polymerization for textile or plastic, advanced biofuel
Spanish broom		Ornamental plant, biomass	Fibre
Safflower	Oil content: 35%, >90% unsaturated fatty acids, ash content of the remaining straw: 10-12%, Cross calorific value: 4300 kcal/kg	Food and feed applications	Biofuels, phytoremediation, advanced biofuels for residual biomass
Nettle	Fiber ca 16%	Mainly pharmacy as medicinal raw material	phytoremediation
Cardoon	Hemicellulose= 16-19% Cellulose= 45-48% Lignin=11-14% Ash= 7-11% Whole plant Higher Heating Value (HHV)= 13-16 MJ kg-1	Traditional Food, Forage, CHP, erosion mitigation, wildlife habitat	Advanced biofuels, bioplastics, phytoremediation, Oil based products
Guayule	guayule rubber (10%), guayule bagasse with resin (20%), bagasse without resin (70%)	guayule rubber, hypoallergenic latex; (wood preservatives, paints and adhesives, from the resin)	specialty chemicals, ethanol
Pennycress	Seed: 30-35% oil. Main FAs: C18:1=9-12%; C18:2=18-20%; C18:3= 12-14%, C20:1= 9-10%, C22:1=37-40%	Biofuel	Aviation
Willow	NDF< 40% ADF= 40-45% Lignin= 18-24% Ash=1- 2% Whole plant Higher Heating Value (HHV)= 18.1-18.3 MJ kg-1	CHP, erosion mitigation, wildlife habitat	Advanced biofuels, phytoremediation
Poplar		Solid biofuel – biomass, fire wood, pellets, boards for pellets, plywood for veranda, wood for furniture,	Phytoremediation, biorefinery. Roof material – shingles
Black locust	Ash content 1-3%, Cross calorific value: 4500 kg/ha	CHP, erosion mitigation, wildlife habitat	Advanced biofuels, phytoremediation
Eucalyptus	Net heating value: 17.3 up to 18.4 MJ.kg-1; ash content: 2-3% (stems), 4.5% (branches)	Cellulose and paper industry, fuelwood, charcoal, poles, shelterbelts, railway sleepers and hardboard production.	production of cellulosic ethanol, phytoremediation, floral nectar for honey, bark for tannin and rutin, leaf oil for industrial purposes and pharmaceutical applications
Siberian elm		Ornamental plant, biomass	
Wild sugarcane	Hemicellulose= 24-26% Cellulose= 37-39% Lignin= 20-22% Ash= 3-5% Whole plant Higher Heating Value (HHV)= 16-18 MJ kg-1	NA	Advanced biofuels, (under investigation for bioplastics, non-wood materials, and ecosystem services)
Lupin		food and pharmaceuticals/cosmetics	
Wild tobacco		NA	NA

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Saltbush	The harvesting material is rich in crude protein 14-21%	Lignocellulosic feedstock for biomass production	Advanced biofuels, phytoremediation
Jerusalem artichoke	Tubers: 20% dry matter of which fibers 15-25% (cellulose), 2% proteins, 3% ashes, 70-80% inulin.	alcohol, fructose, fresh tubers, animal feed	Pharmaceuticals, industrial production of fructose and inulin, biofuel
Kenaf	Ash content: 2-4% (of the stems), the ash content of the core is 1-2% (residual material after taking the bark), 4200 to 4400 (Gross calorific value:kcal/kg)	Biocomposites, insulation materials, animal bedding, bioplastics, textiles	The residual biomass can be used for pellets production and/or as feedstock for advanced biofuels
Sunn hemp	Fiber fractions: 67% cell. 11.8% hemicell. 8.8% lign. Ash 2.5%. Volatile matter 2.5%	Green manure, cover crop, nematode suppressor, fiber crop	Advanced biofuels, bioplastics, phytoremediation
Caper spurge	Seed: oil content 48–52% characterized by cis-12,13-epoxyoleic acid called vernolic acid (58–62%); Oleic acid C18. Leaves: Quercetin; p-coumaric acid; Ferulic acid. Latex: L-dopa; B-sitosterol.	Biofuels, paints, varnishes, adhesives, industrial coatings, medicinal and pharmaceutical product	Industrial applications like epoxy coatings and resins; pharmaceuticals.
Sugar beets	Sugar content of roots 14-21%	Food and forage	Advanced biofuels, butanol
Calendula	oil content 15-25%; main fatty acid, calendic acid 54-63% (C18:3c)	reactive diluent in alkyd paints, medicinal oil; healthcare; wood preservation; non-fogging poly-urethane foam	
True lavender	Flowers: oil content of 0.5 to 1.1%	Essential oil; perfumes, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, personal care and home maintenance products	Aromatherapy, integrative medicine, food supplement